

Integrating Machine Learning and Data Science in Planetary Missions for Science Autonomy

Victoria Da Poian*^{1,2,3} and Eric Lyness^{1,2}

¹NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, Greenbelt, USA

²Microtel LLC, Greenbelt, USA

³Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, USA

Future planetary exploration missions investigating habitability and potential life on distant bodies (e.g., Titan, Enceladus) will face communication constraints with limited transfer rates and short communication windows. Operations of existing missions such as to Mars rely heavily on ground-in-the-loop interactions that may not be suitable for such remote targets [1]. To address this, new missions will require greater autonomy to achieve their desired science return [2].

Our research leverages machine learning (ML) and data science techniques to enable science autonomy onboard space missions [3]. Science autonomy would enable a spacecraft to make closed-loop scientific decisions in situ without the need for constant communication with Earth's science operations teams. It has the potential to greatly enhance decision-making speed, the level of science return, and the overall efficiency of the mission. This paper discusses the current progress and future roadmap for integrating ML and data science in planetary missions to achieve science autonomy.

1 Introduction

Incorporating autonomy in planetary missions is essential to reduce dependence on Earth-based operations and to optimize science return, especially for distant bodies with significant communication delays [4]. Current Mars missions, such as the Curiosity rover, demonstrate the limitations of ground-in-the-loop operations, where scientists on Earth must analyze data and make decisions before instructing the rover on subsequent actions [5].

Our work introduces a framework for achieving science autonomy using data science and ML. This framework aims to transition from ground-based operations to onboard autonomy, thereby improving the mission's responsiveness and data processing capabilities [6].

*Corresponding author. E-Mail: victoria.dapoian@nasa.gov

2 Methods: Data Science and Machine Learning as Tools for Autonomy

In this work, we aim to develop science autonomy to support planetary science operations from the ground in the short term and, in the long term, to enable autonomous operations onboard spacecraft. We utilize computer science tools, including data science and machine learning (ML), to achieve this autonomy.

Data science involves extracting meaningful insights from data through statistical methods, identifying patterns, understanding correlations, and developing data visualizations to communicate findings effectively [7]. Data science provides the foundational techniques for preprocessing and analyzing large datasets, which is crucial for informing ML models and improving their performance [8].

Machine learning (ML), a subset of artificial intelligence (AI), focuses on developing algorithms that learn from data to recognize patterns or make predictions [9]. ML algorithms can be categorized into supervised learning, where input data is labeled and the algorithm learns to predict outcomes for new data, and unsupervised learning, where the goal is to identify patterns and relationships in unlabeled data [10]. Supervised learning techniques are particularly useful for classification and regression tasks, while unsupervised learning methods, such as clustering and dimensionality reduction, are essential for exploratory data analysis [11].

The integration of data science and ML is pivotal for achieving autonomy. Data science techniques preprocess and clean the data, making it suitable for ML applications. Subsequently, ML models can analyze this data to automate decision-making processes, which is critical for autonomous operations in space missions. For instance, data-driven models can optimize

scientific data collection and analysis onboard spacecraft, reducing the need for ground-based interventions [12].

Autonomy in the broader AI context encompasses various fields, including decision-making, planning, and perception [13]. Decision-making algorithms enable autonomous systems to make informed choices based on data inputs. Planning algorithms help in strategizing actions to achieve specific goals, while perception involves interpreting sensory data to understand the environment. The interconnections between these fields are vital for developing robust autonomous systems. For planetary missions, integrating these AI components ensures that spacecraft can perform complex tasks independently, enhancing mission efficiency and success rates.

By leveraging data science and ML, our research contributes to advancing science autonomy. This progress is essential for planetary science, particularly in astrobiology, where autonomous systems must efficiently process and analyze vast amounts of complex data to optimize scientific returns.

3 Results: Applications to Mass Spectrometry Data

We focus on methods for the analysis of mass spectrometry (MS) data as an example of science autonomy to enhance decision-making, speed of science operations, and ultimately the effectiveness of mission science return. Mass spectrometry is an analytical technique used to measure the mass-to-charge ratio of ions [14, 15]. It has a high heritage in space exploration, helping to determine the composition of samples by identifying and quantifying constituent molecules and atoms. Since the 1970s, mass spectrometers have been crucial tools on missions targeting Mars (e.g., Curiosity rover), Jovian and Saturnian moons (e.g., Cassini, Viking, Europa Clipper [16]), the Moon (e.g., LADEE), and outer space (e.g., New Horizons, Voyager). Future planetary missions (e.g., ExoMars, Dragonfly, DAVINCI) will continue to rely on more sophisticated MS instruments capable of generating large volumes of data, which current communication techniques struggle to transmit back to Earth. Limited bandwidth and communication windows present significant challenges for data transmission and mission optimization. Furthermore, interpreting MS data is complex and requires robust analytical models.

3.1 Mars Organic Molecular Analyzer (MOMA)

As a first step towards science autonomy, we applied ML techniques to data from the Mars Organic Molecule Analyzer (MOMA) flight-like engineering test unit (ETU), a dual-source MS-based investigation on the Rosalind Franklin (ExoMars) rover [17]. This enables the science operation team to quickly analyze new MS data and prepare for science-based tactical decision-making during the mission. Initially, we focus on laser desorption mass spectrometry (LDMS) data, as LDMS experiments will be the first tasks performed with the MOMA instrument [18].

Our goal is to develop MS-focused ML techniques that help scientists rapidly analyze samples and make optimized decisions regarding subsequent operations. This effort aligns with the first stages of the science autonomy generation ladder, progressing towards full autonomy where spacecraft can make real-time instrument adjustments and prioritize analyses, optimizing the search for life in our solar system and beyond.

In this research, we developed a three-stage ML pipeline: data processing, filtering using unsupervised learning algorithms to cluster similar data, and matching using supervised learning algorithms to predict the chemical composition of samples (Figure 1). This pipeline exemplifies the progression towards achieving higher autonomy levels by reducing dependence on Earth-based analysis and decision-making.

3.2 Dragonfly Mass Spectrometer (DraMS)

We are also developing peak detection and peak selection algorithms for the Dragonfly Mass Spectrometer (DraMS) to support tandem MS (MS/MS) experiments on the Dragonfly mission targeting Titan [19]. MS/MS involves selecting, fragmenting, and analyzing a specific peak from an initial MS analysis to identify compounds. While MS/MS offers significant opportunities, it also presents challenges due to the communication limitations between Titan and Earth. Our team is developing algorithms to select the most interesting peaks for MS/MS experiments, working closely with the DraMS science team to enable onboard automation of these tasks.

3.3 Ocean Worlds: Chemical Maps for Enceladus and Europa Missions

We are developing novel molecular identification tools for missions to ocean worlds like Europa and Enceladus, which are relevant to astrobiology. Upcoming missions aim to evaluate the habitability and po-

Figure 1: Illustration of the three-stage ML pipeline for LDMS ETU data. Steps include: 1) preprocessing stage where raw LDMS input data are transformed into a ML-readable format; 2) filtering stage using unsupervised ML algorithms for clustering data based on pattern similarities; 3) matching stage using supervised ML algorithms to predict sample types (predictions include “category” and “sample” labels, discussed below).

tential life on these moons, as highlighted in the 2023-2032 Planetary Science and Astrobiology Decadal Survey [2]. We are developing data science and unsupervised ML data processing techniques on MS data from volatile CO₂ equilibrated with laboratory analogs of Europa and Enceladus seawaters as a case study for new strategies for icy ocean world missions [20]. Our goal is to determine whether the mass spectra of volatile gases contain information about seawater composition and potential biosignatures.

By implementing clustering algorithms, we investigate inherent patterns in the spectra and integrate these tools into a ML pipeline for quick data analysis from future ocean worlds missions. We compare dimensionality reduction methods such as Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP), t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE), and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to transform high-dimensional MS data into lower-dimensional spaces. This approach includes a comparative analysis of clustering algorithms to identify clusters associated with experimental conditions like seawater composition and CO₂ concentration. Dimensionality reduction supports the analysis of complex MS data in 2D or 3D formats, facilitating the identification of relevant clusters and offering insights into potential compositional mapping of new seawaters.

4 Discussion and Future Work

We also investigate two significant challenges in developing data science tools for mass spectrometry (MS) data specific to space missions, which are common across most robotic planetary missions. First, the lack of sufficient data volume from these unique and highly optimized instruments to train neural networks (NN), and second, the lack of sufficient results from the system to fully trust its output.

To tackle the first challenge, we analyze the performance of machine learning (ML) algorithms after incorporating augmented data. We discuss adopting transfer learning techniques, which involve fine-tuning a NN trained on large amounts of data from commercial instruments so that it can operate effectively on our limited MOMA dataset. For the ‘trust’ challenge, given the exploratory nature of planetary science where it is not always clear what to expect, we must consider agile ML applications that ensure potentially groundbreaking data is not filtered out. We introduce the concept of a Trust Readiness Level (TRL) for science autonomy, akin to the NASA Technology Readiness Level, to systematically assess and build trust in these ML systems.

The tools we are developing for analyzing MS data in planetary science missions using data analysis and ML algorithms represent the initial steps towards achieving the longer-term goal of science autonomy. By creating automated ML tools capable of prioritizing data transmissions, we aim to address the bandwidth limitations of outer solar system missions. These advancements are envisioned as part of a broader roadmap towards deploying algorithms onboard spacecraft, a prerequisite for achieving the autonomy goals indicated earlier.

Current efforts are also focused on investigating the use of transfer learning to leverage MS data collected from commercial and testbed instruments on Earth. This approach helps overcome the data volume challenge by allowing the algorithms to learn from larger, diverse datasets before being fine-tuned with the limited data available from space missions.

These ongoing developments are crucial for enhancing the decision-making speed and effectiveness of science operations, ultimately increasing the scientific return of missions. As part of our envisioned roadmap, we plan to deploy these algorithms onboard future spacecraft, thus incrementally advancing through the autonomy ladder introduced earlier. This progression from ground-based analysis to full onboard autonomy is vital for optimizing the search for life and other scientific objectives in our solar system and beyond.

5 Acknowledgments

This research is supported within the MOMA project with funding from NASA's Mars Exploration Program (MEP). It has been using the performance computing resources from the GSFC Science Data Processing branch. We thank the group of MOMA scientists who participated in the different workshops, Xiang Li, Melissa Trainer, Desmond Kaplan, Andrej Grubisic, Friso van Amerom, Stephanie Getty, and Marco Castillo, for their guidance and support. We also thank the software team development who supported the project, Joe Cirillo, Sam Larson, Nick Dobson and Joe Avolio.

References

- Chien, S. *et al.* Agile science: Using automated planning and scheduling to enhance scientific return of planetary rovers. *Journal of Field Robotics* (2014).
- NASA. Planetary Science and Astrobiology Decadal Survey 2023-2032 (2022).
- Theiling, B. *et al.* Science autonomy: Applications of machine learning to planetary missions. *Nature Astronomy* (2022).
- Camps, A. *et al.* Autonomy in space missions. *Space Policy* (2020).
- Grotzinger, J. P. *et al.* Mars Science Laboratory mission and science investigation. *Space Science Reviews* (2012).
- Bualat, M. G. *et al.* Autonomous systems for the ISS: Results from the SPHERES facility. *Proceedings of the International Symposium on Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, and Automation in Space* (2014).
- Provost, F. & Fawcett, T. Data science and its relationship to big data and data-driven decision making. *Big Data* **1**, 51–59 (2013).
- Schutt, R. & O'Neil, C. *Doing data science: Straight talk from the frontline* (O'Reilly Media, 2013).
- Mitchell, T. M. *Machine learning* (McGraw-Hill, 1997).
- Goodfellow, I., Bengio, Y. & Courville, A. *Deep learning* (MIT Press, 2016).
- Bishop, C. M. *Pattern recognition and machine learning* (Springer, 2006).
- Huntington, H. *et al.* Machine learning for autonomous space systems. *Nature Astronomy* (2020).
- Thrun, S., Burgard, W. & Fox, D. *Robotic mapping and exploration*. Springer (2002).
- Mahaffy, P. R. Mass spectrometry in the U.S. Space Program: Past, present, and future. *Journal of the American Society for Mass Spectrometry* **10**, 688–695 (1999).
- Chou, J. *et al.* Planetary mass spectrometry. *Annual Review of Analytical Chemistry* (2021).
- Brockwell, S. *et al.* Mass spectrometry in space exploration: Europe's past, present and future. *Mass Spectrometry Reviews* (2016).
- Goesmann, F. *et al.* in *Astrobiology* 655–685 (Mary Ann Liebert, Inc., 2017).
- Da Poian, V. *et al.* Science autonomy: Bringing Artificial Intelligence into Planetary Exploration. *Nature Astronomy* (2022).
- Lorenz, R. D. *et al.* Dragonfly: A rotorcraft lander concept for scientific exploration at Titan. *Johns Hopkins APL Technical Digest* (2018).
- Da Poian, V. *et al.* Exploratory studies on molecular identification using mass spectrometry data for icy ocean world missions. *Journal of Analytical Atomic Spectrometry* (2023).